

3D-CHARACTERIZATION OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Synchrotron microtomography is carried out in situ during thermal cycling of a continuous fibre reinforced MgAl₁₀O₆ matrix. Channel-like porosity is found in the matrix extending along the unidirectional fibres and its evolution during thermal cycling is analysed by means of a channel-recognition algorithm. The volume fraction of the porosity in the composite is significantly reduced after several thermal cycles. The results are used to explain the shrinkage observed during dilatometry experiments of the same continuous fibre reinforced metal.

Keywords: Metal-matrix composites, Synchrotron microtomography, Continuous fibre reinforced composites, Porosity, Thermal cycling.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous C-fibres are used to reinforce light metals in order to achieve improved specific properties such as high stiffness and strength and reduced coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) [1-2]. Although the C-fibres improve the properties of metals in the direction of the fibres, they degrade the metals in the transverse direction [3-5]. The properties of continuous fibre reinforced metals (CFRMs) depend on the distribution and degree of directionality of the fibres [6]. CFRMs are usually produced by infiltration of fibre bundles with the molten metal. This processing route can result in uninfiltated regions and/or the formation of shrinkage pores at the interface between fibres and metal during cooling from the infiltration temperature [2, 7]. These pores can also affect the properties of CFRMs. It is therefore necessary to analyze the different microstructural features to understand the behaviour of CFRMs. This analysis can be performed partially by conventional 2D metallography [8-9] but these methods do not take into account the possibility that the microstructural features may present some degree of curvature along their axis and/or irregular cross-sections. The use of non-destructive 3D characterisation methods such as X-ray computed tomography has shown to be a useful tool to qualitatively and quantitatively characterise the bundles

orientation, local volume fraction and spatial distribution [10]. The same methodology can be extended to detect defects in these materials. The aim of this work is the development of a 3D methodology for the analysis of the evolution of porosity present on CFRMs taking into account that the porosity in this kind of materials tends to take the form of discontinuous channels located along the interface with the continuous fibres. The results obtained are used to interpret previous experimental results concerning thermal expansion of the same CFRM [11].

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials description

A MgAl_{10.6} matrix reinforced with 65 vol% of continuous C40MB-3k carbon fibres with a mean diameter of ca. 7 μm was produced by gas pressure infiltration at Leichtmetall-Kompetenzzentrum Ranshofen / Austria (LKR). Tows of continuous fibres were wound to obtain densely packed unidirectional fibre performs for 2 mm thick plates. These performs were compressed to produce plate-like samples. Additional pressure acted on the fibre bundles by the infiltration front of the non-wetting melt. Figure 1 shows light optical micrographs of the obtained CFRMs looking onto the plane perpendicular to the fibres. Figure 1 a) shows a fibre-free region between two different fibre bundles. It has been shown in [10] that the few fibres located within these matrix channels show larger misorientations compared to the fibres in the fibre bundles. Figure 1 b) shows a region within a bundle with a higher magnification. Touching fibres as well as local variations of the fibre volume fraction can be observed.

Figure 1: Optical micrographs of cross sections of MgAl_{10.6}/C-40MB/65f-UD showing veins between some fibre bundles.

Microtomography

Microtomography (μCT) experiments were carried out at the High-Energy Scattering Beamline ID15 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble, France. A sample of approximately 1x1 mm² cross-section and length \sim 10 mm along the externally observed fibre orientation was prepared. The CFRM sample was exposed to four consecutive thermal cycles as shown in Figure 2. μCT was carried out at the indicated temperatures. The sample was heated using a gas blower. Heating/cooling rates of 3K/min were applied. The holding time required to carry out the μCT at each temperature was around 10 min.

Figure 2: Temperature profile indicating the temperatures at which tomography was carried out (black points).

A cubic voxel size of $(1.6 \times 1.6 \times 1.6 \text{ } \mu\text{m})^3$ was used. The images obtained have a 32 bit floating format and were converted to 8 bits for the processing. The sizes of the reconstructed μCT volumes were $1024 \times 1024 \times 1024$ voxels ($\sim 1.64 \times 1.64 \times 1.64 \text{ mm})^3 \sim 4.4 \text{ mm}^3$. Taking into account the square sections of the samples of approximately $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$, this results in a scanned volume of the samples of $\sim (1 \times 1 \times 1.64 \text{ mm})^3 \sim 1.64 \text{ mm}^3$. The original volumes were cropped into subvolumes of $500 \times 500 \times 500$ voxels = $800 \times 800 \times 800 \text{ } \mu\text{m}^3$ before analysis due to computational restrictions. The crops were done at the same coordinates for all the analysed volumes. This means that the comparisons between the different conditions are not exactly from the same regions because the expansion/compression of the sample due to heating/cooling were not taken into account. However, the maximum displacement of the sample, taking place between RT and 300°C , was determined to be only 40 pixels = $64 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ using the registration tool of VGStudioMax [12]. The tomographic reconstructions showed marked ring artefacts as shown in Figure 3.

These ring artefacts were corrected with the following procedure:

- a) the cropped slices were transformed into polar coordinates using the centre of the ring artefacts as the centre of the polar transformation [13]. This resulted in a picture where the ring artefacts appear as vertical lines.
- b) the vertical lines were filtered using a bandpass filter available in the software ImageJ [14].
- c) the filtered images in polar coordinates were transformed into cartesian coordinates.

The result of the filtering of the ring artefacts can be observed for one cropped slice before and after the correction in Figure 3 a) and b), respectively. The similar X-ray absorption exhibited by the MgAl_{10.6} alloy and the C-fibres does not allow to separate the fibres from the matrix. However, the pores appear as darker areas, i.e. with lower grey values. The pores form elongated structures extending along the fibre direction.

Figure 3: A cropped slice before and after the correction of the ring artefacts.

Methods of characterisation

As already mentioned, the voids located at the interface between the metallic matrix and the C-fibres present mostly a channel-like form. The segmentation of the pores was carried out in two ways in order to separate the channel-like pores from the total fraction of pores. First, the pores within one volume were segmented by grey value threshold. This threshold was estimated by eye and was varied within ± 2 grey values to obtain a systematic error. All the regions larger than 25 voxels ($102 \mu\text{m}^3$) and below the threshold values adopted were considered as pores. Secondly, channel-like pores within the same volume were segmented using the channel-recognition algorithm implemented in [10] for the recognition of continuous fibres in an Al-based CFRM. The minimum dimensions for a possible region to be considered as a channel-like pore were: radius = 2 pixels and length = 5 pixels, i.e. minimum volume = 25 voxels. As a convention for the analysis of the results, the channel-like pores will be called “channels” and the rest will be called “pores” hereafter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the evolution of the total porosity, the channels and the pores during the thermal cycles expressed as a fraction of the initial condition. The systematic error obtained by changing the threshold values in a ± 2 range is within the symbols in the diagram. The total porosity in the sample at the beginning is about 0.1 vol%. The channels represent about 85% of the total porosity volume, while the other pores less than $8\mu\text{m}$ long are only about 15% of the total. There is a general tendency of the

channels and thus the total porosity to be reduced during the thermal cycles, while the fraction of pores remain practically constant. The point at RT after the first 300°C cycle shows an increase of the total porosity and of the channels that do not correlate with the general decreasing tendency observed. This may have to do with a movement of the sample during the variation of the temperature that leads to a comparison of slightly different volumes. The total porosity at the end of the fourth thermal cycle, before rapid cooling down to -30°C , is about 10% of the initial volume fraction. The last condition at RT after the rapid cooling to -30°C shows an increase in factor ~ 5 of the total porosity and channels volume fraction. The volume fraction of pores remains again practically constant.

Figure 4: Evolution of the volume fraction of the total porosity, the channels and the pores during thermal cycling.

Figure 5 show the channels in the conditions A, C, E and F in Figure 4. Interrupted channels touching the border of the analysed volumes are identified as pores. The latter indicates that the volume fraction of channels in Figure 4 is slightly underestimated, while the volume fraction of pores is overestimated. All the volumes shown in Figure 5 present a clustering of discontinuous channels in the fibre-free region separating two bundles observed in Figure 3, which corresponds to one of the slices in the analysed volume. The decrease of the total porosity volume fraction due to the decrease of the fraction of channels with the thermal cycles can be clearly seen comparing the volume in Figure 5. New channels are formed after the rapid cooling to -30°C and the porosity volume fraction increases (Figure 5 F).

Figure 5. Channels in volumes of $500 \times 500 \times 500$ voxels = $800 \times 800 \times 800 \mu\text{m}^3$ for the conditions A, C, E and F in Figure 4.

Figure 6 a) and b) show the length change as a function of temperature during two thermal cycles from -30 to 120°C followed by two thermal cycles from -30°C to 200°C for the same CFRM in the directions longitudinal and perpendicular to the C-fibres, respectively. The heating and cooling rate for these dilatometry experiments was 5K/min as reported in [4] with deformation stages indicated for heating and cooling [11]. The results show a shrinkage of the sample in both directions, longitudinal and perpendicular to the continuous fibres, that increases for each consecutive cycle. This shrinkage amounts 0.015% and 0.02% in the longitudinal and perpendicular directions, respectively. This corresponds to a volumetric shrinkage of about 0.06% . The results obtained in the present study show that the shrinkage of the sample is due to the shrinkage of the channel-like pores during thermal cycling. These channel-like pores are concentrated mainly at the border between fibre bundles and the matrix in the fibre-free zones. This shrinkage amounts about $0.09\text{ vol}\%$, which is higher than the shrinkage observed in the dilatometry experiments due to the higher maximum temperature of the last two thermal cycles used in the present study. This shrinkage of the channels can be understood taking into account the mismatch between the stiff C-fibres and the $\text{MgAl}_{10.6}$ matrix. During heating the metal can expand in the direction perpendicular to

the fibres. However, the fibres will not allow the MgAl0.6 to expand freely in the direction of the fibres (longitudinal direction). The thermal compression stresses in the matrix in the direction of the fibres will rise during heating until thermally activated relaxation starts at about 150°C making it flow into the channel-like pores. During cooling, the matrix will contract again, at first elastically, then reaching tensile yield strength and strain hardening. The composite will not return to the original condition as relaxation is not reversed. At least part of the channels are filled now with matrix resulting in a reduction of the volume of the CFRM. The fact that some of the porosity is not visible after the thermal cycles (see Figure 5) does not necessarily imply that it disappears. It only means that the resolution used for the tomographies is not enough to reveal pores smaller than 102 μm^3 .

Figure 6. Thermal expansion as a function of temperature for the CFRM in a) fibres direction with magnified y-axis and b) perpendicular to the fibres direction

CONCLUSIONS

The evolution of the porosity during thermal cycling has been determined by means of synchrotron microtomography for a continuous fibre reinforced MgAl_{0.6} matrix. The following conclusions can be picked up from the obtained results:

- The individual C-fibres could not be resolved by means of tomography due to the similar X-ray absorption between them and the MgAl_{0.6} matrix. However, porosity could be detected for sizes down to 102 μm^3 using a voxel size of (1.6 μm)³. Phase contrast tomography and holotomography could help to increase the contrast between matrix and reinforcement for this system.
- The original reconstructed tomographic slices show a significant amount of ring artefacts that could be effectively removed using a procedure based on a polar transformation of the images and a bandpass filtering of the rings.
- The volume fraction of the porosity decreases significantly during thermal cycling when the temperature amplitude exceeds 150°C. A reduction of almost 90% of the initial volume fraction is achieved after cooling from 300°C.
- Most of the pores form channels located along adjacent C-fibres. The channel-like pores could be confidently segmented using the channel-recognition algorithm proposed in [10].
- The reduction of the porosity during thermal cycling is governed by the reduction of these channel-like pores. This is proposed to be due to the filling of the channel-like pores during heating by relaxation of the creeping MgAl_{0.6} matrix. These results can be correlated with the observed shrinkage of the same CFRM during dilatometry experiments.

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